

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ALGORITHMIC AND SOFTWARE SUPPORT FOR THE CLASSIFICATION OF OBJECTS OF AUTOMATED EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract — Automated educational systems account and classification of account objects issues are investigated in this article. To analyze LMS systems that develop accounts, classification and to study them by their specification considered to be the main object in this article.

Keywords — Automated educational systems, LOG, protocol events, classification, representative of reference class

INTRODUCTION

In organising educational process in higher educational institutions and in controlling it automated educational system MOODLE [1-2] is used. Professors teachers and students are using this system effectively. Teachers create their own course elements in this system and students do their tasks according to these materials. These tasks are evaluated by professor- teachers and the system itself. To cut it short, educational process is organised; student's knowledge is evaluated and educational system is controlled in this way. To learn aimed automated systems that performed in this way, to control their activity and monitoring is one of the basic objectives of present day educational system.

Dynamic algorithm of automated educational systems account classification is elaborated, and due to it, algorithm of system database research objects classification task solution is developed.

Imagine, to use the system, one of the courses are given. So, this course is prepared by professor- teachers and is put into the system; learners, students and teachers of this course are formed.

It is required: to identify if the course composition is complete; to identify when, where and which course elements are addressed by users; to solve such tasks as identification of quality index of effective using the course included to system.

Usually, to solve these issues, events list- files in chronological order used in big information systems are used. In some literature, [4-11] they are called “journal, report, registration file (инг. Log)”.

Log-information consisted of special files, they are forming executed works in the system by users and programmes, as well as reports of executed events with the system and save it.

To identify education quality, to organise and control it, to analyse how online technologies are effective, addressing to system by users, to know to what extent is important works they have done, to

which resource is being addressed, from which IP address have user entered, declarations to the system and their geography, the activity of students and teachers in the system, the level of usage of resources put in the system(addressing to them, copying out and etc.), execution of tasks and texts, also evaluation of students and other variety of things are made on the basis of these events reports.

It is not a secret that in higher educational institutions “Educational information controlling systems” (EICS) is widely used in order to support traditional education (or to complete some elements of it)

Educational Institutions through EICS is not able to do monitoring of process completely, however, EICS forms big data enable to do monitoring.

We are required in order to do monitoring of system, to classify this BIG DATA finding and visualize them.

The main issue is to analyze reports of formed events by LMS systems, classification, to learn them by their specifications and etc.

Fig1. Forming process classification of data in EICS

Let's address to account in order to solve the given task. Based on the following account data, report material created by Moodle system is illustrated below.

The screenshot shows a Moodle system report with columns for 'Время', 'Пользователь', 'Значение', 'Конкретное событие', 'Компонент', 'Название события', 'Описание', 'Источник', and 'IP адрес'. It lists several events such as 'Зачетная книжка' and 'История в избранное' with associated user IDs and IP addresses.

Fig2. The picture of report formed by Moodle system on the basis of account

Moodle system save each movement of user. The figure shows simple report of account created by Moodle system.

Teachers can monitor the students of this course: what do they do, when and where do they do, also they can watch how students answer the test questions.

Of course, these reports are useful, but they are not enough. For example, information below cannot form Moodle system.

1. How many times student was member for the course?
2. How many tests (questions) included to LMS?
3. How many tests are passed in LMS?
4. How many declarations have been made in LMS forums ?
5. How many times resources have been added to LMS and etc.

Moodle relying on its standart abilities, cannot form such data. In order to solve the problem, it is required to analyze data which placed in Moodle account.

Below, the real view of account in database that is given for analysis is shown (in order to easily describe the data, csv format is used)

```

\core\event\user_enrolment_created;core;created;user_enrolment;user_enrolments;2534;c;0;947;50;90;1275;90;1275;0;"a:1:{s:5:"enrol";s:4:"self";};";1431421985;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
\core\event\course_viewed;core;viewed;course;NULL;NULL;r;2;947;50;90;1275;90;NULL;0;"N";1431421986;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
\mod_quiz\event\course_module_viewed;mod_quiz;viewed;course_module;quiz;28;r;2;8511;70;2524;1275;90;1275;0;NULL;0;"N";1431422036;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
\core\event\role_assigned;core;assigned;role;role;5;c;0;947;50;90;1276;90;1276;0;"a:3:{s:2:"id";i:2997;s:9:"component";s:0:"";s:6:"itemid";i:0;};";1431422041;web;192.168.0.130;NULL
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_started;mod_quiz;started;attempt;quiz_attempts;204;c;2;8511;70;2524;1275;90;1275;0;"N";1431422123;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_viewed;mod_quiz;viewed;attempt;quiz_attempts;204;r;2;8511;70;2524;1275;90;1275;0;"a:1:{s:6:"quizid";s:2:"28";};";1431422124;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_viewed;mod_quiz;viewed;attempt;quiz_attempts;204;r;2;8511;70;2524;1275;90;1275;0;"a:1:{s:6:"quizid";s:2:"28";};";1431422157;web;188.113.200.236;NULL
    
```

The data is described in other way in the table below.

Table 1

eventname	objecttable	objectid	contextid	contextlevel	contextinstanceid	userid	courseid	relateduserid	anonymous	timecreated	origin	ip
\core\event\user_enrolment_created	user_enrolments	2534	947	50	90	1275	90	1275	0	1431421985	web	188.113.200.236
\core\event\role_assigned	role	5	947	50	90	1275	90	1275	0	1431421985	web	188.113.200.236
\core\event\course_viewed	NULL	NULL	947	50	90	1275	90	NULL	0	1431421986	web	188.113.200.236
\mod_quiz\event\course_module_viewed	quiz	28	8511	70	2524	1275	90	NULL	0	1431422036	web	188.113.200.236
\core\event\user_enrolment_created	user_enrolments	2535	947	50	90	1276	90	1276	0	1431422041	web	192.168.0.130

eventname	objecttable	objectid	contextid	contextlevel	contextinstanceid	userid	courseid	relateduserid	anonymous	timecreated	origin	ip
\core\event\role_assigned	role	5	947	50	90	1276	90	1276	0	1431422041	web	192.168.0.130
\core\event\course_viewed	NULL	NULL	947	50	90	1276	90	NULL	0	1431422041	web	192.168.0.130
\mod_quiz\event\course_module_viewed	quiz	28	8511	70	2524	1275	90	NULL	0	1431422074	web	188.113.200.236
\mod_quiz\event\course_module_viewed	quiz	28	8511	70	2524	1275	90	NULL	0	1431422092	web	188.113.200.236
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_started	quiz_attempts	204	8511	70	2524	1275	90	1275	0	1431422123	web	188.113.200.236
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_viewed	quiz_attempts	204	8511	70	2524	1275	90	1275	0	1431422124	web	188.113.200.236
\mod_quiz\event\attempt_viewed	quiz_attempts	204	8511	70	2524	1275	90	1275	0	1431422157	web	188.113.200.236

In order to classify above mentioned data with EICS that was given in figure 1, the algorithm was elaborated, as a result of processing data and classification, we can identify which event in system has happened and how many times it has happened. Moreover, we will have the graphic below.

Fig 3. The graphic formed by “The course module viewed” parameter.

Presented data is the small part of processed data, and in fact, it is possible to form many graphics on the basis of account that can satisfy the customer.

The mathematical consideration of the task. Imagine, that account is given in table presented below.

$$X = \left\{ \begin{matrix} x_1^1, x_1^2, \dots, x_1^N \\ x_2^1, x_2^2, \dots, x_2^N \\ \dots \\ x_n^1, x_n^2, \dots, x_n^N \end{matrix} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Here X – is the system, elements of account, the complex of events happening by system users, made works are $x_i = (x_i^1, x_i^2, \dots, x_i^N)$ and i -is

object of the table (event). Each x_i –event is the complex of $x_i \in X$ events, and regards to them.

The table of events are required to classify X -events into different classes. That is, events complex have to be clustering.

Thus, X –events should be divided into such m -classes, that these classes shouldn't cross with each other:

$$X = X_1 \cup X_2 \cup \dots \cup X_m, X_1 \cap X_2 \cap \dots \cap X_m = \emptyset.$$

In the third figure graph, the number of declarations to the course elements are described. In its turn, the course elements the “course module viewed” value is equal to 1, and it means that declaration has happened.

The same **mod_quiz_events** – The events of test module, that is the test element parameters consist of the following. If test element object is signed with e_1 vector, than

$$e_1 = (e_1^1, e_1^2, \dots, e_1^N), \quad e_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \text{бунда } i = \overline{1, N}$$

Here e_1^i -vector parameters can be defined as follows:

- e_1^1 = attempt abandoned (rejected);
- e_1^2 = attempt became overdue
- e_1^3 = attempt deleted;
- e_1^4 = attempt preview started ;
- e_1^5 = attempt reviewed;
- e_1^6 = attempt started;
- e_1^7 = attempt submitted;
- e_1^8 = attempt summary viewed;
- e_1^9 = attempt viewed;

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